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Close Reading Revisited: Formalism in Literary Studies

The Revised K to 10 Curriculum for English uses literature as its main component to deliver the lessons needed for Junior High School students. From Philippine Literature to English Literature, a student needs to understand literary pieces using different approaches. For the teacher, this becomes a challenge in balancing theoretical correctness with classroom accessibility. Among the available approaches, Formalism is one of the most practical for teaching literature. Formalism is a general approach that treats literature as a unique form of human knowledge to be examined on its own terms. It focuses on form over content. This centers on the idea that literary work should be understood through its form, structure, and language, which, when thoroughly applied, becomes a powerful tool for discussing literary pieces.

Jose Garcia Villa's Sonnet 1 presents the elements of writing a poem. Although this is for a poem, it is closely related to the focus of the Formalist Approach. According to his poem, a good literary piece should have a rhythm. Another, it should contain rhyme and figurative language. Rhythm, rhyme, and figurative language alongside plot, characterization, imagery, symbolism, tone, and structure are the elements one needs to look into if using Formalism as an approach to literary criticism. Using these different elements of literature, students will focus on what is present within the text itself. Thus, close reading should be developed among the learners while using this approach.

Teaching the Formalist Approach to students, especially those in Junior High School, is helpful for them to understand the literary piece. The elements of prose and poetry are being discussed across grade level and this is helpful in teaching them the approach. Using a close reading activity would be of great help, where students will analyze a poem line by line while identifying the different literary devices used and discussing the effects of these devices on the poem. In addition, graphic organizers can help the students break down elements such as plot structure or character development. Essay writing can also be used where students are tasked to write a reflection using textual evidence and focused analysis.